

Heterogeneous CPU plus GPU approaches for HEVC

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Abstract The High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) standard has opened the door to high quality multimedia contents and new formats such as Ultra High Definition (UHD) as a result of the unceasing demands of the market. This standard is able to outperform prior standards by up to 50% in terms of perceptual video quality, but at the cost of extremely large computational complexities. For this reason, the development of fast coding algorithms is now a requirement to make HEVC an adequate candidate for real-world scenarios. In this regard, this paper proposes a collaborative CPU+GPU coding architecture for this standard, in which the CPU performs a coarse-grained parallelization of the encoder, while the GPU carries out a fast motion estimation. Given that the GPU algorithm can work together with a wide variety of parallel algorithms, this paper evaluates two of them: tiles, defined in the standard, and slices, already present in previous standards. Results indicate that slices are more adequate in terms of parallel efficiency ($10.75\times$ speed-up on average using 12 threads), while tiles achieve better coding efficiency.

Keywords HEVC · H.265 · Parallel Encoding · GPU · Tiles · Slices

1 Introduction

Since its ratification more than a decade ago, the H.264/Advanced Video Coding (AVC) [1] standard established itself as the most widespread video

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compression standard for many types of applications and scenarios, including Blu-ray and various high-definition (HD) television broadcasts. Nevertheless, the consumption pattern of video contents has changed in recent years, with higher preference for larger resolutions such as ultra high definition (UHD), and higher quality of contents. This, however, has led to an increase in bit rate that could become a relevant problem from the point of view of communication networks and storage services. For these reasons, the Joint Collaborative Team on Video Coding (JCT-VC) defined the High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) standard in early 2013 [2]. This standard has been designed to support very large resolutions and formats while improving the coding efficiency of previous standards. In fact, HEVC roughly doubles the rate-distortion (R-D) performance of H.264/AVC. In other words, it is able to reduce nearly 50% bit rate for the same perceptual video quality [3]. This notable improvement in coding efficiency comes, however, at the expense of extremely high computational complexities [4].

The HEVC standard is based on the same block-based scheme as its predecessors. The improved efficiency is derived from the enhancement of many existing coding tools, as well as the introduction of new ones. Among others, these tools include a highly flexible quadtree partitioning scheme that divides the picture into square blocks named coding tree units (CTU). While these tools enable good coding efficiency, they imply a huge increase in encoding time. To reduce the processing time, HEVC introduces some high-level tools, such as tiles [5] and wavefront parallel processing (WPP) [6], with the aim of enabling the parallel encoding and decoding of a video sequence. These parallelization techniques rely on creating partitions that are processed concurrently. However, some dependencies are broken to achieve this concurrency.

The parallel techniques defined in the standard operate at a coarse-grained level, while the rest of encoding operations are sequential. In fact, some of these operations can involve large computation times. In particular, the inter prediction module can take more than 60% of the encoding time in Random Access configurations [7]. This module is responsible for determining the motion vectors (MVs) that minimize the R-D cost of matching each of the blocks in which the picture is divided with respect to temporal neighbors. Given the nature of this operation and the large number of repetitive operations performed, an auxiliary device such as a graphic processing unit (GPU) could help reduce the time devoted to the inter prediction [8].

In this regard, this paper introduces a GPU-based heterogeneous coding architecture in which several picture partitions are processed in parallel in the CPU, and the integer motion estimation (ME) algorithm of the inter prediction module is performed in a single GPU, creating a collaborative framework between both devices. The main purpose of the proposed architecture is to reduce the total processing time of the encoder, which is achieved at the cost of minimal coding efficiency losses. This architecture, however, admits a wide variety of coarse-grained parallel techniques. Concerning the two approaches defined in the standard, the nature of tiles is more suitable for GPU architectures, as the shape of the partitions promotes data locality [9]. Nevertheless,

Fig. 1 Example partitioning of a frame into tiles and slices

it is important to emphasize the similarities of tiles and slices, which are also regions that can be processed independently. In this regard, the main aim of this paper is to analyze the scalability and the coding efficiency of the aforementioned architecture when used in conjunction with these two techniques, showing that slices provide better parallel efficiency than tiles, whereas the latter achieves better coding efficiency on average.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a short summary of HEVC. Section 3 covers some of the most relevant related works in the topic. Then, Sect. 4 provides an overview of the proposed GPU-based heterogeneous coding architecture. An experimental evaluation is carried out in Sect. 5, showing the results of this architecture in terms of time reduction and coding efficiency, and a comparison between tiles and slices. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Sect. 6.

2 Technical background

As mentioned in the introduction of this paper, HEVC achieves considerably higher coding efficiency compared with previous standards by enhancing existing coding tools and introducing new ones. In this regard, one of the most important novelties introduced by HEVC is the new picture partitioning scheme, which is now based on a quadtree structure called CTU [3]. These structures can be partitioned, in turn, into coding units (CU), prediction units (PU) and transform units (TU). PUs store prediction information such as MVs, and can range from 64×64 to 8×8 using either symmetrical or asymmetrical sizes. For this purpose, HEVC defines eight possible partitions for each CU size: $2N \times 2N$, $2N \times N$, $N \times 2N$, $N \times N$, $2N \times nU$, $2N \times nD$, $nL \times 2N$ and $nR \times 2N$. These new sizes involve a large increase in the complexity of the encoder, but it also enables larger adaptability for edges, especially with larger CU sizes. To get more accurate motion vector predictors (MVP), the standard defines the advanced motion vector prediction (AMVP) algorithm, which enables the derivation of several most probable candidates based on data from adjacent PUs. As a result, less bits are necessary to encode the MVs.

All these new coding tools introduced in HEVC enable a very flexible encoding. Nevertheless, they also involve a notable increase in the computational

complexity of both the encoder and the decoder. With the aim of reducing this complexity, the standard defines two different parallelization strategies known as tiles and WPP, which were already mentioned above. On the one hand, tiles are rectangular partitions where dependencies are partially broken across boundaries, making it possible to process them independently. The in-loop filters can still cross these boundaries, however, to improve the overall coding efficiency. An example of tile-based processing can be seen in Fig. 1a, in which the input picture has been divided into 9 tiles. On the other hand, WPP enables the creation of rows that can be processed in parallel. In this case, unlike tiles, the entropy coding is allowed to cross partitions with the aim of minimizing coding losses, but at the cost of introducing a delay of two CTUs between consecutive rows, which limits the parallelism of the algorithm. As a design decision, both techniques cannot coexist at the same time.

Apart from tiles and WPP rows, the input frames can also be divided into partitions that already exist in previous standards called slices. A slice is a region of the frame that can be independently decoded with regard to other slices in the same frame. The size and shape of a slice can be arbitrary, although it is required that the CTUs contained in it are consecutive in coding order, as shown in Fig. 1b. Their main aim is to avoid the error propagation in multimedia transmissions. However, they have been largely used in the past as a way of parallelism due to their versatility. As a counterpart, slices introduce additional bits that involve overhead in terms of coding efficiency.

3 Related work

As mentioned previously, the coding efficiency obtained by HEVC comes from the improvements introduced in the modules that are part of the encoder. For this reason, one of the most relevant challenges faced by the research community is to reduce the total encoding time while maintaining the coding efficiency of the standard. The approach followed by many related works is to achieve this reduction from an algorithmic point of view. In this regard, pruning the decision tree to skip partitions in which it is unlikely to find a better prediction candidate than the current one has proven to be one good way to notably reduce the total encoding time. For example, it is possible to terminate the CTU partitioning at an early stage by determining the spatial and temporal homogeneity of the pictures [10]. Similarly, the same authors proposed a series of fast encoding algorithms based on the prior detection of smooth regions in the input images [11]. Different approaches include, for example, the use of pre-analysis techniques to assist the encoding process [12]. While the main aim of these algorithms is to reduce the encoding time, they perform their operations on a different level than the proposed CPU+GPU approach, and thus are complementary.

Given the need for parallel techniques in HEVC, several state-of-art works address the complexity analysis and parallelization strategies of this standard [7, 13]. As for other parallelization techniques, authors in [14] present a

variation of WPP called overlapped wavefront (OWF), which enables processing two consecutive pictures at the same time to avoid ramping inefficiencies. In this way, when a thread finishes processing a CTU row and there is no more available rows in the current frame, it can begin processing the next picture instead of idling. However, this paper applies this technique to the decoder side. With regard to the encoder, authors in [15] propose a fine-grained parallel optimization of the ME module for multi-core and many-core platforms, allowing to perform the MV prediction of all PUs available in a CU at the same time. Therefore, the maximum parallelism will be dependent of the platform. In a similar way to this work, a ME algorithm for many-core platforms is presented in [16].

Other works make use of GPU devices in the encoding process, especially to perform inter prediction. Authors in [17] propose a scheme designed for GPU plus multi-core CPU platforms, in a similar way to this paper. However, the encoder used in the tests does not include all the coding tools, and thus results are not comparable. In [18], authors propose a GPU-based ME algorithm that makes use of a diamond search pattern, which might not obtain the best candidate in some cases. This work was later extended for bi-prediction in [19], but still used the same search pattern. Additionally, the achieved speed-up is limited due to the portion of time devoted to the ME, which could be solved with the use of a coarse-grained algorithm.

4 CPU plus GPU heterogeneous coding architecture

As detailed in the previous sections, it is possible to parallelize both the encoder and the decoder using the techniques defined in the standard or by using slices. While this is an effective way to reduce the total encoding time, some modules still involve large computation times, which should be reduced to achieve reasonable processing times. The module in which it is devoted the largest amount of time is the inter prediction module, which basically consists in subtracting the current PU to different positions in the reference frame, in order to reduce the R-D cost generated by a given MV. The nature of this operation makes the GPU a very adequate auxiliary device to perform the whole processing in little time. For this reason, in this paper we propose a GPU-based heterogeneous coding architecture in which the CPU performs a coarse-grained parallelization of the encoding, while the GPU carries out a fine-grained parallelization of the ME algorithm of the inter prediction module. In this way, it is possible to archive much larger speed-ups than using a homogeneous parallel architecture.

As mentioned in Section 2, a tile is a partition that can be independently encoded or decoded with regard to other tiles in the same frame. They were introduced in the standard because of the huge parallelism they offer, and also due to their ability to delimit regions of interest in the picture. Given that WPP introduces unwanted synchronization points, tiles become a more suitable alternative in terms of parallelism and scalability [7]. Similarly, the

Fig. 2 Distribution of CTUs among all available threads

absence of synchronization points of the slices within a frame also offers good level of parallelism, but unlike tiles, they cannot be easily shaped to fit the features of the image. Nevertheless, slices have been traditionally utilized also in previous standards. In this regard, both slices and tiles were considered for the proposed heterogeneous architecture, with the aim of comparing their scalability and the parallelism offered by both techniques.

Our proposed approach is to divide each frame into as many tiles or slices as available processing units. In this way, if a hardware platform is composed of an octa-core CPU, each frame would be divided into eight different tiles or slices. While tiles can be assigned any rectangular shape defined by parameter, the approach followed in this paper is to utilize only horizontal tiles. The reason for this is to improve the data locality in the GPU, as frames are usually stored in raster scan order, and also to make a fairer comparison with slices, whose CTUs are always consecutive also following this order. Additionally, in order to maximize the parallel efficiency of the algorithm, each partition is assigned the same number of CTUs, if possible. In order to avoid costly memory transfers, this approach has been implemented following a shared memory scheme, in which a synchronization point is required at the end of the frame to keep the decoded picture buffer up to date. An example of the CTU distribution performed in a quad-core platform is shown in Fig. 2.

With regard to the GPU, it is responsible for performing the ME. This operation consists in estimating the motion vectors (MV) that perform the transformation of the PUs in the current frame with regard to the reference frames with the lowest R-D cost. Due to the large amount of repetitive operations required by the ME, this algorithm fits perfectly into the GPU architecture and its massive data processing capabilities. In particular, the proposed heterogeneous architecture has been provided with the GPU-based integer ME algorithm described in [8]. This algorithm is able to operate asynchronously from the CPU, providing it with the motion information of one CTU ahead. This information includes the distortion costs in terms of sum of absolute differences (SAD) of all of the possible MVs in the search area for each PU and each reference frame. In this way, the encoder only needs to perform the sub-pixel refinement and the bipredictive search.

The proposed heterogeneous architecture combines both the tile-based or the slice-based parallel algorithm, and the GPU-based integer ME algorithm. Every processing unit queues the ME algorithm into different streams of the

Fig. 3 Example of the proposed heterogeneous architecture using tiles with 4 threads

same device, making it possible to execute the kernels concurrently with respect to the CPU. As a result, the GPU utilization increases, and the total power consumption decreases. An example of this architecture using tiles is shown in Fig. 3. The scalability of the proposed architecture depends on two different factors. Firstly, on the number of partitions allowed in the bitstream, which might be as high as the total number of CTUs in the picture. Secondly, on the hardware platform itself, as the GPU could limit the amount of parallelism if it is not able to process all the required CTUs simultaneously. This condition, however, has not occurred in the development of our experiments.

5 Performance evaluation

The experiments were executed on the HEVC Test Model (HM-16.3) reference software [20], following the guidelines and coding conditions provided by the JCT-VC in [21]. In this regard, Random Access became the selected configuration, and the QP values are 22, 27, 32 and 37. The encodings were carried out using the Main profile and 8-bit depth. Sequences of classes A to D according to the JCT-VC classification were used, which include the following resolutions: 2560×1600 (A), 1920×1080 (B), 832×480 (C), and 416×240 (D).

The hardware platform used in the experiments is composed of an Intel® Xeon® E5-2650 v2 CPU running at 2.60 GHz and an NVIDIA® Tesla® K40 GPU. The encoder was compiled with GCC 4.8.5 and NVIDIA® CUDA 7.0, and executed on CentOS 7. Turbo Boost was disabled to achieve the reproducibility of the results.

With regard to the parametrization of the encoder, the sample adaptive offset (SAO) filter was disabled, as well as the *LFCrossSliceBoundary* flag. The

Table 1 Per-sequence results of the proposed GPU-based heterogeneous architecture using tiles varying number of threads

Class	Video sequence	BD-rate (%)					Speed-up				
		1	2	4	8	12	1	2	4	8	12
A	Traffic	0.45	0.64	1.03	1.84	2.67	1.05	2.01	3.82	6.88	9.17
	PeopleOnStreet	-0.13	0.06	0.42	1.07	1.72	1.12	2.14	4.09	7.24	9.57
B	Kimono	0.50	1.07	2.19	4.15	6.03	1.09	2.09	3.95	7.03	8.26
	ParkScene	0.22	0.47	1.07	2.16	3.21	1.06	2.03	3.69	6.48	7.99
	Cactus	0.32	0.71	1.64	3.18	4.54	1.08	2.04	3.68	6.62	7.98
	BasketballDrive	2.99	3.68	4.78	7.07	9.12	1.13	1.99	3.73	6.76	7.89
	BQTerrace	-0.24	0.14	0.96	2.33	3.59	1.06	2.01	3.77	6.69	7.99
C	BasketballDrill	-0.15	0.79	2.66	6.06		1.10	2.06	3.79	6.99	
	BQMall	0.79	1.88	3.76	7.14		1.08	2.05	3.53	6.66	
	PartyScene	-0.20	0.23	0.98	2.34		1.07	1.97	3.68	6.95	
	RaceHorses	0.52	1.38	3.18	6.25		1.14	2.03	3.87	7.28	
D	BasketballPass	0.38	2.47	5.25			1.11	2.05	3.38		
	BQSquare	0.06	1.23	2.93			1.05	1.85	3.35		
	BlowingBubbles	-0.26	0.65	2.33			1.05	1.89	3.34		
	RaceHorses	-0.30	1.30	4.05			1.11	1.89	3.49		
Mean values (A & B)		0.59	0.97	1.73	3.12	4.41	1.09	2.04	3.82	6.82	8.41
Mean values (all)		0.33	1.11	2.48	3.96	4.41	1.09	2.01	3.68	6.87	8.41

reason for this decision is to achieve full independence between tiles, as the SAO filter might introduce some dependencies in the encoding. The executions were performed using 1, 2, 4, 8 and 12 threads. The GPU was enabled in all cases, but the tile-based parallelization was disabled in the case of using one thread. The results of using one thread will thus reflect the effect of the GPU-based algorithm in the encoding.

The results will be provided in terms of speed-up and Bjøntegaard delta rate (BD-rate). The latter represents the percentage of bit rate variation between two sequences with the same objective quality [22]. Therefore, a negative value implies that the proposal improves the coding efficiency of the baseline encoder. The speed-up was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Speed-Up} = \frac{T_{\text{baseline}}}{T_{\text{proposal}}} \quad (1)$$

where T_{baseline} and T_{proposal} represent the total encoding time of the baseline encoder and the proposed scheme, respectively.

Table 1 shows the results obtained by the proposed architecture when using tiles and varying the number of threads. It can be seen that the tests were not carried out for class D when 8 and 12 threads were used, and for class C with 12 threads. This is caused by the fact that the maximum parallelism of the tile-based coarse-grained algorithm is limited by the total number of rows in the frame, and these classes include lower resolution sequences. Considering that the average values shown in the table might not comprise the same set of

Table 2 Per-sequence results of the proposed GPU-based heterogeneous architecture using slices varying number of threads

Class	Video sequence	BD-rate (%)					Speed-up				
		1	2	4	8	12	1	2	4	8	12
A	Traffic	0.45	0.75	1.29	2.49	3.52	1.05	2.05	3.82	7.32	10.54
	PeopleOnStreet	-0.13	0.11	0.51	1.27	1.99	1.12	2.18	4.11	8.00	11.56
B	Kimono	0.50	1.22	2.67	5.34	7.94	1.09	2.05	3.96	7.63	11.01
	ParkScene	0.22	0.59	1.41	2.93	4.45	1.06	2.05	3.88	7.38	10.58
C	Cactus	0.32	0.83	2.09	4.06	6.24	1.08	2.11	4.06	7.52	10.47
	BasketballDrive	2.99	3.81	5.16	7.97	10.71	1.13	2.10	3.84	7.35	10.43
D	BQTerrace	-0.24	0.34	1.50	3.73	5.69	1.06	2.00	3.84	7.44	10.68
	BasketballDrill	-0.15	1.07	3.63	8.40	10.99	1.10	2.06	3.80	6.99	9.20
E	BQMall	0.79	2.23	4.96	10.04	12.93	1.08	2.05	3.54	6.66	8.88
	PartyScene	-0.20	0.39	1.52	3.68	5.24	1.07	1.96	3.69	6.94	9.23
F	RaceHorses	0.52	1.53	3.67	7.45	9.07	1.14	2.03	3.87	7.31	9.81
	BasketballPass	0.38	3.09	7.33	12.30	16.39	1.11	2.04	3.38	4.80	5.49
G	BQSquare	0.06	2.28	6.42	13.20	19.29	1.05	1.86	3.35	4.64	5.34
	BlowingBubbles	-0.26	1.36	4.69	9.43	13.50	1.05	1.90	3.32	4.57	5.21
H	RaceHorses	-0.30	1.78	5.70	9.84	13.13	1.11	1.88	3.49	4.95	5.73
	Mean values (A & B)	0.59	1.09	2.09	3.97	5.79	1.09	2.08	3.93	7.52	10.75
Mean values (all)		0.33	1.42	3.50	6.81	9.41	1.09	2.02	3.73	6.63	8.94

Fig. 4 Coding efficiency results of the tile-based and the slice-based heterogeneous architectures

results, the average values for classes A and B are also shown to better reflect the effect of the proposed architecture. Likewise, Table 2 shows the results obtained by the slice-based architecture. As can be seen, the results obtained with one thread are the same as those obtained by the tile-based algorithm, as only the GPU is enabled in this case. It can also be observed that the slice-based algorithm allows 8 and 12 threads. Unlike tiles, in which the pictures are divided into rectangular rows using horizontal borders, slices can be more flexible, so that more than two slices can coexist in one row of CTUs.

First, it is worth detailing the results obtained by the GPU-based ME algorithm itself. It can be seen that the achieved speed-up is limited to $1.09\times$,

Fig. 5 Speed-up results of the tile-based and the slice-based heterogeneous architectures

which is derived from the fact that this is the portion of time devoted by the encoder to the unipredictive integer ME in the inter prediction module. Nevertheless, this time reduction is achieved at the expense of very low coding efficiency losses of 0.33% on average. In fact, it can be seen that in some sequences the coding efficiency improved with respect to the baseline encoder, which is caused by the exhaustiveness of the full search carried out by the GPU-based algorithm, in contrast to the simplified search performed by the baseline encoder. It should also be noted that this speed-up will perform as a multiplier factor for the speed-up achieved by the coarse-grained parallel algorithm.

When compared with other related works, our proposed GPU-based ME shows significant advantages. For example, even though the method proposed by *S. Radicke et al.* [18, 19] involves shorter processing time in the device, the limited exhaustiveness of this method results in higher coding efficiency penalties in comparison with the GPU-based ME used in this paper. In particular, this method exceeds 1% BD-rate on average for the Low Delay P configuration.

With regard to the joint algorithm, it can be seen that the coding efficiency experiences larger losses when the number of processing units increases, using either tiles or slices, as shown in Fig. 4. In fact, the BD-rate follows a linear behavior with respect to the number of threads. This is the expected behavior of the algorithm, as more dependencies are broken, and thus less neighbors are available for prediction. This effect can be observed primarily in low-resolution sequences, e.g. classes C and D, with a lower number of CTU rows.

The tables also display the speed-up obtained by the proposed joint algorithm, which can reach a factor of up to $9.57\times$ with 12 threads for tiles, and $11.56\times$ for slices. This means that the proposed architecture is considerably more parallel efficient using slices than tiles, as shown in Fig. 5. This is caused by the fact that the slices enable a more even partitioning of the pictures than the horizontal tiles, and thus the total number of CTUs is evenly distributed among the available threads. In this way, even though the achieved speed-up is logarithmic with respect to the number of threads, it exhibits a virtually linear behavior for high-resolution sequences.

6 Conclusions

The HEVC standard has enabled the advent of a great number of applications and video formats such as UHD, as a result of the demands of the market for higher quality of video contents. Nevertheless, the improved coding efficiency of HEVC has also led to a relevant increase in computational complexity of both the encoder and the decoder. The research community is making large efforts to develop algorithms and techniques that enable to reduce this complexity with the aim of making this standard feasible for real-world scenarios. Accordingly, this paper proposes a CPU+GPU collaborative framework for HEVC in which the CPU performs a coarse-grained parallelization of the encoding, while the GPU aids in carrying out the ME. The experimental evaluation of the algorithm showed that it reached a speed-up of $8.41\times$ on average for classes C and D with 12 threads using tiles, and $10.75\times$ using slices, which showed the limitations of tiles in terms of parallel efficiency and scalability. On the contrary, with regard to coding efficiency, the tile-based approach provided lower penalties than slices, as the latter breaks more dependencies.

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